

A Systematic Review of Theoretical Perspectives and Technology-Based Strategies for Fostering Critical Thinking Skills in the Age of Misinformation

Ram Das Rai
IDP in Educational Technology
Indian Institute of Technology Bombay
Mumbai, India
214383001@iitb.ac.in

Sahana Murthy
IDP in Educational Technology
Indian Institute of Technology Bombay
Mumbai, India
sahanamurthy@iitb.ac.in

Abstract— This paper is a systematic review of the literature on critical thinking (CT) and misinformation, with the purpose of exploring how they are conceptualized, theorized, and addressed by various theoretical perspectives and technology-based strategies. This topic is important as misinformation poses serious threats to individuals and society, and critical thinking is vital for discerning and evaluating information sources. The review methodology involved using the PRISMA framework to search 10 databases and finalized 49 papers for this systematic review. The review brings together knowledge from multiple domains such as philosophy, psychology, digital literacy and technology to identify best practices for designing a technology-enhanced learning (TEL) environment that fosters critical thinking skills in students. The findings show that critical thinking is a dynamic and evolving skill that requires constant practice, updating, and media literacy skills. The review also suggests several technology-based strategies for dealing with misinformation and promoting critical thinking, such as cognitive tools, digital fact-checking tools and platforms, gamification, and interactive learning tools. Furthermore, it recommends that technology-enhanced learning environments for critical thinking should consider the cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects of this skill, and provide learners with authentic and meaningful tasks that require them to apply their critical thinking skills in real-world situations.

Keywords—Technology-enhanced learning (TEL) environment, Critical thinking skills, Misinformation, Media literacy

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Prevalence of misinformation in the digital age

Online misinformation, including fake news and viral deception, undermines democracy, shared truth, and public trust [6] [33] [34] [44]. Misinformation refers to unintentionally misleading information, while fake news deceitfully mimics real news articles without journalistic standards [6] [13] [26] [31]. Large volumes of fake news spread easily on social media and may influence events [15] [34] [43].

Recent systematic reviews concerning misinformation have highlighted that scholarly investigations have centred around defining misinformation, probing its causes and effects, and assessing potential solutions [34] [43] [44]. This includes analysing false content, writing style, distribution patterns, and source credibility [44]. Though a small number of people directly encounter misinformation, effects can be significant for some prone to biases, selective exposure, lack of critical thinking, and repeated exposures [29] [34].

Technical challenges also exist due to online content volume and diversity, where intent and facts cannot always be computationally determined [43].

Social media prioritizes engagement over accuracy through personalized, selective content reinforcing views [7] [18] [19]. This can lead to echo chambers and incomplete judgments relying on heuristics rather than logical evaluation [19]. Detection and downranking efforts have limitations and do not fully address cognitive susceptibility [6] [13] [18].

Developing critical thinking skills to independently evaluate information rationally shows promise [6]. Critical thinking includes analysing arguments and evidence to form reasoned opinions [19]. Cultivating these skills can help resist misinformation while contributing accurate information [6] [19] [29]. Interdisciplinary collaborations remain important for explainable, efficient detection methods [43] [44].

B. Importance of critical thinking in combating misinformation

Recent systematic reviews emphasize that critical thinking is a crucial skill for judging the quality of online information and spotting fake news [1] [21]. Critical thinking involves abilities like analysing arguments, making inferences through inductive and deductive reasoning, judging claims, and solving complex problems [20]. It also involves being open-minded, inquisitive, flexible, seeking reasons, and considering diverse perspectives [20]. However, background knowledge alone is insufficient for critical thought; these skills develop from an early age but deficiencies still exist in adults [20].

There are a few potential solutions to discern accurate from inaccurate online information. One approach is educating end-users on critical evaluation [11] [18]. People are more susceptible to believing false claims if they rely more on intuition than critical thinking [18]. Personal deliberation and focusing on accuracy can help people distinguish facts from falsehoods, especially when providing reasoning [18]. Additionally, in the digital environment, there is the capability for microtargeting individual beliefs through recommendation feedback loops [11]. This phenomenon underscores the importance of equipping users with the skills to critically assess the information they encounter online.

Another strategy is reason-checking news content through assessing argument quality [26]. The online sphere fuels both misinformation, which is misleading without intent, and disinformation, which is intentionally deceptive [26]. While fact-checking combats falsity, prebunking targets distortions more effectively [26]. As advocated, critical thinking allows

identifying misleading claims by evaluating argument flaws, as news acts as a form of argumentation to convince audiences [26]. The presence of fallacious reasoning therefore signals questionable information [26]. Educating critical evaluation and reason-checking news are approaches to discern accuracy online [18] [26].

II. OBJECTIVES AND METHOD

A. Purpose and objectives of the paper

The present research offers a fresh perspective on the intertwined subjects of critical thinking and misinformation, distinguishing it from prior research conducted by other authors. This study blends the concepts of critical thinking and misinformation, recognizing their interconnectedness in the digital age. This fusion provides a more comprehensive understanding of how critical thinking can effectively counter misinformation.

Furthermore, the current study introduces an innovative solution in the form of a technology-enhanced learning (TEL) environment. This approach acknowledges the role of technology in contemporary education and employs it to cultivate critical thinking skills tailored to address the challenges posed by misinformation in the digital era. This practical dimension differentiates the current research by not only pinpointing issues but also providing a potential solution.

Additionally, this study formulates specific guiding questions for its investigation:

- How is critical thinking defined and conceptualized in the context of misinformation?
- What are the main theoretical frameworks for understanding and addressing critical thinking and misinformation?
- How can technology be used to support critical thinking and counter misinformation?

These guiding questions structure the study's systematic approach, facilitating deeper insights and offering a more comprehensive perspective compared to the broader reviews conducted by earlier researchers.

Moreover, this research places significant emphasis on practicality by illustrating how critical thinking skills can be applied in everyday life. By bridging the gap between theory and real-world application, this practical orientation renders the research accessible and relevant to a wider audience.

Another notable aspect of this study is its interdisciplinary approach. By integrating elements from the fields of education, technology, and media literacy, this research provides a fresh and comprehensive outlook on addressing the intricate challenges of misinformation while fostering critical thinking skills.

This paper explores how critical thinking can effectively combat misinformation in the digital age and puts forth a design for a learning environment that imparts critical thinking skills. The paper comprises six sections: Section II outlines the research objectives and methodology, Section III presents the research findings on critical thinking and misinformation, Section IV discusses the research's contributions and limitations, and proposes a design for a critical thinking learning environment. Finally, Section V

concludes the paper with a summary, reflection, and future directions.

Fig. 1. PRISMA analysis details

B. Method

The authors adopted the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework to conduct this study and select the relevant papers [23]. Their research topic was ‘review and design of a technology-enhanced learning environment for critical thinking and misinformation’. They searched 10 journal databases using the following keyword string: (“information literacy” OR “media literacy” OR “digital literacy”) AND (“critical thinking” OR “critical evaluation”) AND (“misinformation” OR “fake news”) AND (“technology” OR “e-learning”). They applied three levels of filtering to the search results, as shown in Figure 1. First, they limited the results to peer-reviewed research articles published in English between 2013 and 2023. Second, they excluded duplicate records (n = 90), records without an abstract (n = 180), records with irrelevant titles (n = 1010), and Google Scholar entries beyond the first 60 (n = 9,010). For example, a paper titled *New Dialogues in Spanish and Portuguese Studies: Pedagogical and Theoretical Perspectives from the Digital Humanities* was removed because it was not related to their research topic. Third, they analyzed the abstracts of the remaining 363 records and checked if they addressed either or both of the following criteria: (a) the problem of misinformation, and (b) the ways to teach critical thinking skills using technology. Only the papers that met at least one of these criteria were included in the final list which was a total of 49 papers (access the full list here: <https://shorturl.at/dszE8>). To ensure reliability of the study results, the abstracts of a sample of 10 finalized records were independently reviewed and coded according to the selection criteria. Inter-rater agreement was calculated using percentage agreement where there was an agreement on 9 out of 10 abstracts, resulting in an inter-rater agreement percentage of 90% [3]. Any disagreements were discussed and the issue was resolved by consensus. Finally, the authors also manually calculated the frequency of major themes in all papers.

III. FINDINGS

The findings of this study reveal how critical thinking is defined, conceptualized, and applied in the context of misinformation. The study also identifies the key components and skills associated with critical thinking, as well as the role of critical thinking in discerning and evaluating information sources. Furthermore, the study explores the theoretical lenses that can be used to examine critical thinking and misinformation, such as cognitive approaches and literacy perspectives. Finally, the study presents some technology-based strategies that can help deal with misinformation and develop critical thinking, such as cognitive tools, digital fact-checking tools and platforms, and gamification and interactive learning tools.

Fig. 2. A block diagram of the findings on critical thinking and misinformation

A. Understanding Critical Thinking

1) Definitions and conceptualization of critical thinking in the context of misinformation

Critical thinking (n=64) was one of the most observed themes in literature. Critical thinking is a key pillar of media literacy, as it enables individuals to make true and reasonable decisions about their actions or the accuracy of information [26]. Critical thinking is a purposeful, self-regulatory judgment that involves interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, and explanation based on various considerations [26]. Similarly, scholars suggest that effective critical thinking involves a logical approach, inquisitiveness, objectivity, and reliance on evidence [40]. Critical thinking requires the examination and evaluation of ideas, arguments, and information to ensure their quality and accuracy [28]. An adequate critical thinker is habitually inquisitive, well-informed, trustful of reason, open-minded, fair-minded in evaluation, prudent in making judgments, willing to reconsider, diligent in seeking relevant information, reasonable in selecting criteria, and focused in inquiry [28].

2) Key components and skills associated with critical thinking

Critical thinking is a complex and multifaceted ability that involves various cognitive skills and attitudes, as well as methods and technologies to evaluate and process information. According to a group of experts, some of the cognitive skills that enable critical thinking are logical thinking, inference skills, and the ability to identify and avoid logical fallacies and cognitive biases [40]. Both, logical fallacies (n=23) and cognitive biases (n=66) were highly observed themes in the literature. Apart from abilities, critical

thinkers should have attitudes such as inquisitiveness, objectivity, and reliance on evidence, which motivate them to seek out relevant and reliable information, to question their own assumptions and perspectives, and to base their judgments on facts rather than opinions or emotions. Additionally, critical thinkers should be able to evaluate the credibility of web information by checking author information, publication date, and comparing sources, as well as to detect and avoid misinformation, disinformation, and propaganda [40]. Furthermore, some experts suggest that critical thinking also requires the ability to design and implement activities to improve student's critical and analytical thinking skills, especially for teachers who want to foster critical thinking in their students [4] [32]. They also emphasize the importance of reading and writing skills, as well as skills for comprehending, interpreting, analysing, and criticizing texts, for effective communication and understanding of different types of texts. Finally, another expert propose that technologies can also support critical thinking by providing tools and platforms that facilitate information access, analysis, synthesis, and presentation, as well as enhancing user engagement and motivation [8]. However, they also argue that these technologies should prioritize information gain over attention capture and that they should be ethical, fair, and unbiased systems that respect users' rights and values.

3) The role of critical thinking in discerning and evaluating information sources

One of the main strategies to mitigate the effects of fake news and viral deception is to promote media literacy and critical thinking skills, which can help people differentiate between what is real and what is fake, and identify sources of information that are credible and reliable [30] [38]. Critical thinking has been an object of discussion across disciplines ranging from Philosophy to Psychology to Informal Logic, and it has become a key pillar for media literacy [26]. Critical thinking involves the assessment of the quality of arguments that constitute a news claim, and the recognition of arguments that are fallacious or misleading, such as cherry-picking, false analogies, and hasty generalizations [26]. To exercise critical thinking skills, people can use various methods of prebunking, which are ways to inoculate people against fake news before they encounter it. Prebunking methods can be fact-based, logic-based, or source-based, and they can instruct people against misleading rhetorical strategies and content features that make fake news spread fast [26]. In addition to education and awareness campaigns that teach people how to prebunk fake news and viral deception, social media platforms can also play a crucial role in combating them. They can invest in algorithms and tools that can detect and flag fake news and viral deception, and they can also promote credible sources of information and provide users with the tools to verify information [38].

B. Theoretical Lenses for Examining Critical Thinking and Misinformation

1) Cognitive approaches

The cognitive approach is a theoretical lens that examines how individuals process and evaluate new information in relation to their existing knowledge and beliefs [8]. According to cognitive dissonance theory, people tend to assess new information based on its compatibility with their prior beliefs, which requires cognitive effort. Cognitive dissonance (n=2)

was observed as theme in at least two papers in the literature. Confirming preexisting beliefs generates positive affect, while encountering opposing information triggers negative affect [8]. However, this approach also reveals the challenges and limitations of critical thinking and misinformation in the digital age.

One of the challenges is the backfire effect, which occurs when directly confronting misinformation to debunk it leads to further reinforcement of confirmed beliefs due to the increased availability of evidence [8]. Backfire effect (n=5) was observed as theme in multiple papers in the literature. Another challenge is the illusory truth effect, which occurs when people perceive repeated statements as more credible, creating a false sense of familiarity and validity [33]. Maya Shankar, a behavioural scientist, suggests that when people hear something repeatedly, they may not remember its truthfulness but find it recognizable [11].

The cognitive process approach identifies four components through which people interact with fake news: reception, information acceptance, cognitive integration, and sharing [33]. Reception refers to how misinformation captures the attention of internet users. Negativity bias and the illusory truth effect are two factors that influence reception. Negativity bias makes individuals more focused on negative information, which is prevalent in fake news. The illusory truth effect leads individuals to perceive repeated statements as more credible, creating a false sense of familiarity and validity [33].

Information acceptance, the second component, involves evaluating the truth value of information to decide whether to integrate it into one's knowledge network. This evaluation can be analytical, intuitive, or lacking in evaluation, depending on cognitive effort and motivation. However, truth evaluation can be biased by various factors, such as cultural identity, personality traits, and pre-existing knowledge and attitudes. These factors make certain concepts appear more fluent and truthlike than others [28]. Additionally, confirmation bias plays a role, as individuals actively seek and accept information that aligns with their worldview while dismissing contradictory information [33]. Humans also struggle to identify deception, often perceiving information as reliable [33]. These biases make people more susceptible to fake news during the information acceptance process.

Cognitive integration, the third component, involves assimilating accepted information into existing knowledge networks. Misconceptions can arise if integrated information or its semantic relationships are missing or false, resulting in fragmented and inaccurate conceptions of the world [33]. Confirmation bias reinforces these misconceptions through selective exposure to information that aligns with existing misconceptions, leading to larger flawed knowledge structures. This can foster a cognitive state known as naïve realism, wherein individuals perceive their perspective as the only valid one and dismiss alternative information as irrational or biased [33]. Filter bubbles created by algorithms that recommend customized content based on users' previous history can further limit exposure to diverse perspectives, exacerbating vulnerability to fake news [36]. Sharing, the fourth and final component of the cognitive process approach, refers to how the integrated information is disseminated among internet users, especially on social media platforms [33].

2) Literacy perspectives

Fake news and misinformation are pervasive problems in the digital age, and they require effective strategies to counteract them. Literacy can be an effective educational strategy in this regard. Not surprisingly, literacy (n=700+) was the most observed theme in the literature, it consisted of multiple sub-themes like information literacy (n=88), media literacy (n=592), digital literacy (n=24), critical literacy (35), data literacy (n=30) etc. Information literacy is the ability to find, evaluate, and use information effectively and ethically [33]. Information literacy interventions aim at enhancing the cognitive processing of online news by fostering self-evaluation of knowledge and skills, knowledge construction and reorganization, and knowledge and skills transfer [12] [25] [33]. However, the positive effects of information literacy on debunking fake news are rather limited, and more research is needed to explore the effectiveness and applicability of information literacy interventions in different settings and populations [33].

Another strategy to counteract fake news is media literacy and critical literacy, which are skills of critical "reading" and evaluation of information in the digital age [9] [11] [14] [35]. Media literacy and critical literacy can provide a pre-emptive safeguard against misinformation by increasing the awareness of the four processes of interacting with fake news: reception, information acceptance, cognitive integration, and sharing [33]. For example, at the reception level, news recipients need to be warded against emotional framing and the impacts of negativity bias, which are powerful mass communication methods that can influence their attention and beliefs [33]. Approaches based on inoculation theory provide one way of fostering such healthy scepticism towards emotional content [33]. Therefore, media literacy and critical literacy are crucial skills to resist fake news illiteracy, which can fuel flawed evaluation of news and misinformation processing, and result in change resistant misconceptions [15] [24] [33] [39].

C. Technology-Based Strategies to Deal with Misinformation and Develop Critical Thinking

1) Cognitive tools

One of the technology-based strategies to deal with misinformation and develop critical thinking is to use cognitive tools, which are digital tools that enhance cognitive processes such as reasoning, problem-solving, and decision-making [2]. Cognitive tools can help people to evaluate and construct arguments, which are essential skills for critical thinking and media literacy. For example, various computer software packages have been created to support argument mapping, which is a technique for visualizing the structure and quality of arguments [26]. Some of these software packages are Araucaria, iLogos, Rationale, and LiteMap [26]. The educational efficacy of these tools has been tested across different domains and contexts, and they have been shown to improve critical thinking skills and outcomes [26]. Another example of a cognitive tool is a chatbot that provides participants with good arguments rebutting the most common counter arguments against genetically modified organisms, with the aim of preventing the formation of misconceptions [26]. Chatbot (n=5) was observed as theme in at least two papers in the literature. The ArgTech research centre has also showcased how argument technology can be applied to the media sphere, teaching how to improve debate skills and appraise argumentative structures in news reports, with the goal of instilling those critical literacy skills needed to reduce polarization and strengthen communication persuasive skills

[26]. Therefore, cognitive tools can be useful and effective strategies to counteract misinformation and foster critical thinking in the digital age.

2) *Digital fact-checking tools and platforms*

Another technology-based strategy to deal with misinformation and develop critical thinking is to use digital fact-checking tools and platforms, which are digital tools that verify the veracity and reliability of information and sources. Digital fact-checking tools and platforms can help people to evaluate the credibility of news claims, which can be influenced by various characteristics of posts or of people's interaction with them, such as number of quoted sources, prior exposure to a claim, official-looking logos and domain names, post topic and author username, etc. [18]. However, digital fact-checking tools and platforms also face some challenges and limitations, such as the nuance, subtlety, and open-texture of statements that make the veracity of statements much fuzzier than a simple true–false distinction. Therefore, many fact-checking organizations do not check facts as much as provide interpretation, contextualization, and exegesis [26]. Moreover, some digital fact-checking tools and platforms also incorporate other features and functions, such as recommendation systems that nudge people to make better news consumption choices or recommender systems that explain interface where users' emotional profiles are factored in the interaction with pedagogical agents who compare and contrast various stances of an issue [5] [26] [42]. Therefore, digital fact-checking tools and platforms are diverse and complex strategies to counteract misinformation and foster critical thinking in the digital age.

Some other examples of technological tools and platforms to counter misinformation are social media monitoring tools, image verification tools, natural language processing (NLP) tools, and deep learning algorithms. Social media monitoring tools help to monitor social media platforms for fake news and malicious viral content, and to identify suspicious content, bots, and fake accounts [10] [38]. Image verification tools help to detect fake news and malicious viral content by verifying the source and authenticity of images used in news articles and social media posts, using techniques such as reverse image search and metadata analysis [38]. NLP tools help to analyse the language used in news articles and social media posts to detect fake news and malicious viral content, using machine learning algorithms to identify suspicious language patterns, such as the use of emotive language, hyperbole, and exaggeration [31] [38]. Deep learning algorithms help to analyse large amounts of data to identify patterns and trends that indicate fake news and malicious viral content, using machine learning techniques to analyse social media activity, including likes, shares, and comments [16] [27] [31] [38]. Therefore, these digital fact-checking tools and platforms use various techniques and algorithms to verify the veracity and reliability of information and sources in the digital age.

3) *Gamification and interactive learning tools for critical thinking development*

Digital games are digital tools that engage and educate users through interactive and immersive scenarios. Game (n=299) based learning was one of the most frequent technology-based strategy to teach critical thinking and fight misinformation. They can help users to learn and practice the skills of identifying and resisting misinformation and disinformation, by exposing them to the methods of persuasion and manipulation used by fake news producers and

spreaders. For example, some digital games teach users how to recognize misleading sources, headlines, or images, through trial and error, e.g., Fakey, NewsWise, and Real or Photoshop [22] [26]. Some other digital games simulate the decision-making processes of communication gatekeepers' e.g., BBCireporter and NewsFeed Defenders [26]. A more sophisticated generation of digital games cast the player as the "fake news spreader" who learns by doing successful misleading strategies used by disinformators, e.g., Bad News, Go Viral!, and The Harmony Square [26]. Impact evaluations have shown that these tools are highly advantageous and effective in inoculating users against misinformation and disinformation [11] [26]. Therefore, digital games are useful and engaging strategies to counteract misinformation and foster critical thinking in the digital age.

One example of a digital game that aims to counteract misinformation and foster critical thinking is Chamber Breaker (CB), which is a game-based system designed to help increase one's awareness of and respond to the echo chamber effect. The echo chamber effect is a phenomenon where people are exposed to only like-minded information and peers, and ignore or reject alternative information that contradicts their views [33]. CB has been designed based on psychological concepts, such as inoculation, heuristics for judging, and gamification. Inoculation is a strategy that exposes people to weakened versions of fake news arguments and refutes them, in order to increase their resistance to misinformation and disinformation [26]. Heuristics for judging are mental shortcuts that people use to evaluate the credibility and reliability of information and sources, such as the number of quoted sources, the official-looking logos and domain names, etc. [18]. Gamification is a strategy that enhances intrinsic motivation by employing game-like elements, such as problem-solving, engaging storylines, and game mechanics (e.g., scores, tokens, achievement badges) [19]. Gamification can effectively promote self-awareness, user engagement, and feelings of excitement, fun, and desire, while inducing improvements in targeted behaviours [19]. CB incorporates these psychological concepts in its design and features. For example, the story of CB reflects the process of creating the echo chamber phenomenon, where people in the game scenarios support the polarized opinions posted by the player [19]. CB also provides score-winning, score-balancing, and badge-winning functions to reward the player for completing the tasks [19]. Therefore, CB is a digital game that can help people become more aware and critical of the echo chamber effect and its consequences.

IV. DISCUSSION

This paper aims to enhance critical thinking in the context of misinformation, which is a dynamic and evolving ability that requires constant practice and updating. To address the first research question, the paper synthesizes the main concepts, definitions, and frameworks of critical thinking from various disciplines and perspectives. Critical thinking can be defined as a purposeful, self-regulatory, and logical judgment that involves interpretation, analysis, evaluation, inference, and explanation of ideas, arguments, and information based on various considerations, such as evidence, criteria, context, and perspectives. To address the second research question, the paper reviews the main theoretical frameworks for understanding and addressing misinformation, such as information literacy, media literacy, and critical literacy. These frameworks can help understand

and address the cognitive processes and challenges involved in interacting with misinformation. It also highlights their interrelationships and complementarities.

The paper argues that critical thinking and misinformation are not only individual phenomena, but also social and cultural ones, as they are influenced by the information sources, platforms, and networks that people use. Moreover, it suggests that critical thinking is a complex and multifaceted ability that involves cognitive, affective, and behavioral aspects, as well as the use of appropriate methods and technologies to access, evaluate, and process information. Therefore, the paper proposes that technology-enhanced learning environments for critical thinking should consider these factors and provide learners with opportunities to develop their cognitive skills and attitudes, as well as to engage in authentic and meaningful tasks that require them to apply their critical thinking skills in real-world situations.

To address the third research question, the paper discusses some of the technology-based strategies that can support critical thinking and counter misinformation, such as cognitive tools, digital fact-checking tools and platforms, gamification, and interactive learning tools. It also explores how digital games can be effective and engaging tools that can help users to learn and practice the skills of identifying and resisting misinformation and disinformation. Digital games can expose users to the methods of persuasion and manipulation used by fake news producers and spreaders, as well as make them more aware and critical of the cognitive and social phenomena that influence their information behavior.

As discussed before, critical thinking is not only an individual skill, but also a social and collaborative practice that involves communication, interaction, and feedback from others. Therefore, technology-enhanced learning environments for critical thinking should provide learners with opportunities to participate in social and collaborative activities that require these skills. Moreover, the paper suggests that learners should develop their digital literacy skills, such as evaluating information credibility, detecting and avoiding misinformation, disinformation, and propaganda, and using technology ethically and responsibly [7] [41]. These skills are essential to cope with misinformation in their daily lives and to foster a culture of critical thinking and information literacy among learners, educators, and citizens. The paper also implies that policymakers should promote ethical standards and regulations for the production and dissemination of information in the digital media, and support the development of digital citizenship and civic engagement among the public. Additionally, the paper suggests that technology-enhanced learning environments for critical thinking should foster learners' awareness and responsibility for their information behavior and its consequences for themselves and others.

The findings of the analysis on the frequency of major themes in literature shed light on the prevalent strategies employed by researchers to combat misinformation. Among these strategies, critical thinking (n=64) emerges as a popular approach in tackling the challenges posed by misinformation. It is evident that researchers recognize the significance of developing the ability to identify logical fallacies (n=23) and cognitive biases (n=66) as essential components of critical thinking. Moreover, the emphasis on media literacy (n=592) in the realm of research stands out, signifying its prominence

as a domain to address misinformation effectively, surpassing other literacies such as information literacy (n=88), digital literacy (n=24), critical literacy (n=35), and data literacy (n=30). Remarkably, the utilization of a game-based approach (n=299) in interventions aimed at combating misinformation and promoting critical thinking is noteworthy, suggesting the effectiveness and attractiveness of gamification in educational initiatives.

Based on the findings of this paper, it can be claimed that to effectively foster critical thinking skills to deal with misinformation, a TEL environment requires various resources that support different aspects of learning. One of these resources is a collaborative platform that enables students to collaborate and engage in peer discussions through features such as discussion forums, chat functionalities, and shared document editing capabilities. This platform facilitates social interaction and knowledge construction among students. Another resource is authentic problem scenarios that are based on real-world issues or current events and involve misinformation. These scenarios allow students to explore and analyze the challenges associated with misinformation and apply their critical thinking skills in realistic contexts. A third resource is tools for information evaluation that help students evaluate the credibility and reliability of information sources, such as fact-checking websites, guidelines for source evaluation, and critical thinking frameworks (like the Paul-Elder Critical Thinking Framework). These resources provide students with criteria and strategies to assess the quality and accuracy of information. A fourth resource is collaborative argument mapping tools (like Rationale) that support collaborative sense-making and critical analysis of information. These tools allow students to visually map out arguments, identify logical fallacies, and assess the strength of evidence. They also enable students to compare and contrast different perspectives and viewpoints on a given issue. A fifth resource is peer feedback and reflection opportunities that foster critical thinking and collaborative learning. These opportunities allow students to provide constructive feedback on each other's arguments and evidence, as well as reflect on their own learning process and outcomes. These resources are based on the findings of a research study which designed and evaluated a TEL environment for misinformation literacy [18].

Apart from the above resources, the TEL environment also needs to implement two instructional strategies that are based on the findings of two research studies [18] [33]. These strategies are: problem-based learning and action-based sharing. Problem-based learning is a pedagogical approach that engages students in collaborative problem-solving of real-life scenarios that require them to construct and apply conceptual knowledge of fake news characteristics and mechanisms [37]. These scenarios are presented in a detailed and realistic way, using interactive media elements to contextualize the problem, and divided into manageable parts that can guide students' work process. Problem-based learning also provides instructional guidance that can scaffold the problem-solving process, especially for students who are not familiar with the learning domain, such as worked out examples, instructional videos, or question prompts. Moreover, problem-based learning stimulates interactive activities that foster social knowledge construction and student engagement, such as group discussions or peer review, and provides guidance and structure for group work and discussions, such as instructor questions or question prompts.

Furthermore, problem-based learning involves using digital tools that facilitate collaborative learning, such as discussion boards, etherpads, or wikis, which allow synchronous collaboration. Problem-based learning can also motivate students to self-evaluate their existing knowledge and skills, and to initiate conceptual change when they encounter information that contradicts their prior beliefs or expectations. Action-based sharing is a design feature that requires students to perform some actions before sharing any content, such as clicking a button, choosing a tag, or writing a comment, to indicate whether they think a story is accurate or not and why. These actions are intended to be simple and quick, similar to current sharing behavior, but also to encourage students to reflect on the information they share and to become aware of the value framing techniques and the illusory truth effects that can influence their judgments. These actions can also prompt students to rely less on their intuition and more on their analytical information processing, which is a more deliberate and effortful way of evaluating information. By integrating these two instructional strategies, researchers can create effective TEL environments to combat misinformation and develop critical thinking in students.

This paper has some limitations that need to be acknowledged. Firstly, the systematic review process employed in this study involved multiple filtering levels based on specific criteria. Unfortunately, this rigorous filtering process may have resulted in the exclusion of potentially interesting and relevant papers due to its strict and narrow criteria. Secondly, although the paper effectively explores cognitive and literacy theories as theoretical frameworks to understand and address cognitive processes and challenges associated with misinformation, it overlooks other significant theoretical frameworks, such as social psychology theories. This omission of social psychology theories was a direct result of that fact that none of the 49 shortlisted papers used such a theory. Lastly, the paper adequately investigates technology-based strategies that support critical thinking and combat misinformation, including cognitive tools, digital fact-checking tools and platforms, gamification, and interactive learning tools. However, it fails to delve into the integration of Computer Supported Collaborative Learning (CSCL) principles, which could facilitate collaboration within technology-enhanced learning environments. This gap in the research also connects with the limitation of not exploring theoretical frameworks like social psychology theories.

V. CONCLUSION

Misinformation is a serious problem in the digital age that requires critical thinking skills. Critical thinking is the ability to use logic, reasoning, and evidence to process information and arguments. This paper reviews the literature on critical thinking and misinformation, and proposes a design of a technology-enhanced learning (TEL) environment that can support these skills. This paper contributes to the knowledge and practice in the field of TEL, and provides practical guidance for policy makers, educators, researchers, and individuals who want to promote critical thinking and combat misinformation.

This paper has some suggestions for individuals, educators, and researchers. Individuals should critically examine digital information, diversify and balance their information intake, use critical thinking and digital tools for media literacy, and seek feedback and dialogue with others. Educators should include critical thinking and misinformation

topics in the curriculum and learning objectives, use various pedagogical approaches and methods, model critical thinking and information behavior in their teaching practice, and encourage learners to reflect on their learning. Researchers should collaborate with other researchers from different disciplines and perspectives, conduct more empirical or experimental studies with diverse populations and contexts, and test the proposed design of TEL environment for critical thinking from this paper.

Based on the previously discussed limitations, the paper suggests some future research directions. Firstly, future studies should conduct a more comprehensive and inclusive systematic review of the literature on critical thinking and misinformation. Secondly, future studies should explore other theoretical frameworks that can help understand and address the social and emotional aspects of critical thinking and misinformation, such as social psychology theories. Thirdly, future studies should investigate how computer-supported collaborative learning (CSCL) principles can be integrated into the proposed design of a TEL environment for critical thinking.

This paper hopes to inspire more research and practice on this topic, as well as more awareness and responsibility among information consumers and producers. This paper believes that critical thinking is a vital skill for individuals to navigate the complex and dynamic information landscape in the digital age. This paper also believes that technology can play a significant role in supporting critical thinking and counteracting misinformation.

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